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Communication Issues in a Multicultural Church: A Case Study of The Good Tidings Church, Ogbomosho, Nigeria

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Abstract

The great commission includes all distinct people groups on the earth while the New Jerusalem shall also be home to all diverse tongues and tribes (Matthew 28:19-20; Revelation 7:9). The Church who engages in the work of global evangelisation and preparing the saints for heaven cannot be less of a multicultural entity. However, intercultural communication issues within diverse cultures have become a barrier to fulfilling God's purpose in the emerging multicultural church. Therefore, arising from a participant's observation of a multicultural church, this article reports common communication issues and suggests multidimensional approaches to address them. This paper adopts a descriptive study design, integrating participant observation and a comprehensive literature review to investigate the communication challenges that emerge when disseminating the Gospel across cultural boundaries. The Good Tidings Church in Ogbomosho is used as a case study to illustrate these dynamics within a multicultural church system. This research suggests that the church can serve as a model and an agent for building a fair, equitable, and just society. This can be achieved by implementing the approaches discussed in this study, which promote the inclusion of all cultures, regardless of social, economic, gender, or ethnic differences.

Keywords: **Communication Models, Cultures, Intercultural Communication Issues, Multicultural Church, the Good Tidings Church, Ogbomosho**

Introduction

The church is a social organisation and a living organism. As a social organisation, relationships exist between members of her community at formal and informal levels. The church possesses organs and systems

that work interdependently despite their unique differences as living organisms. Therefore, as a social organisation, the church is bound to have communication issues (Ray, 2013) as influenced by the varying cultures of its members. Cultures influence how we perceive and understand others differently from us, thus creating barriers in relationships and Communication (Emetuche, 2009). Multiculturalism is a diversified cultural representation within a given demographic entity. Urbanisation, globalisation, immigration, and internal displacements, among other reasons, are the identified causes of cultural diversity. Multiculturalism phenomenally includes the church as an integral part of the emerging society. Hence, the justification for undertaking this study is to describe issues of intercultural communication within a multicultural church and their practical solutions. Communication issues in a culturally diversified Church mount barriers that undermine its formation's very intent and purpose. The purpose hitherto is to include all races, ethnic groups, and nations into the family of God (Ephesians 2:11-22, Revelation 7:9). Cultural diversity by all intent is supposed to be a hallmark of a healthy New Testament Church fulfilling the mandate of the great commission. This great commission includes all nations (*ethnos* – people groups) according to Matthew 28:19. The Good Tidings Church, as a multiethnic missions-oriented church in Ogbomoso witnessing across cultural barriers, provides a context to analyse these issues by these authors. This paper attempts to identify, discuss and proffer solutions to the communication problems consequent to the cultural diversity in a multicultural Church context in Nigeria using descriptive and participant observer methods.

Consequently, it suggests approaches to limit the negative impacts of multiculturalism's communication problems in the local church using effective means along the lines of intercultural contacts within the New Testament Church. The recommendations in this paper will encourage church planters and cross-cultural missionaries to develop the communication skills required for effective leadership and ministry in a culturally diversified context. In addition, they promote social cohesion that cuts across cultural, traditional, societal, ethnic, and racial biases or barriers. This paper presents the multicultural church as a New Testament church model where all ethnic identities are recognised

without room for ethnic hegemony but for social justice, equity, and fairness in the church and the larger society.

Multicultural Emphasis of the New Testament Church

This section discusses the theological understanding of the cultural diversity of the New Testament Church. Emetuche (2009) argues against church growth scholars such as Donald A. McGavran and C. Peter Wagner, who claim that the average homogeneous churches will likely grow more rapidly than the multiethnic ones on the basis and assert that "people like to become Christians without crossing racial, linguistic, or class barriers (McGavran, 1990)." Emetuche asserts that the homogenous Church system reinforces racial segregation and cultural polarity, which often engender attitudes of cultural superiority and exclusiveness. He opines that the principle of homogeneity cannot be justified from biblical or theological points of view.

Padilla (1995) identifies in the New Testament, among other things, that without prejudice to race, riches, or social class, the Gospel was proclaimed by the early church as the works of grace and not of works. Thus, the barriers of segregation were removed among people of diverse backgrounds in Christ Jesus. The Apostles rejected assimilationist racism that compelled the Greek converts to be circumcised before the assurance of full salvation and consequently never intended to form a homogenous Judaistic Church. The Antioch Church and other Churches planted in Asia Minor during Paul's missionary journeys reflected a multicultural representation typical of most cities and metropolia in the Greco-Roman world. Scriptural pieces of evidence abound that reinforce the all-inclusiveness of *missio Dei* to involve all of humankind.

First is the choice of Simon the Cyrene (Cyrene is a city in northern Africa in Libya) to carry Jesus' cross to Golgotha in Matt. 27:32. Second is the representation of diverse tribes at the advent of the Holy Spirit during Pentecost, evidenced by speaking of new diverse tongues understandable to the multicultural worshippers in Jerusalem at that time, according to Acts 2:4-12. The third is the great commission in Matthew 28:19, which includes all humankind and ethnic groups (*ethnos*). The fourth instance is observed when the power of the Spirit was given in Acts 1:8 for witnessing the Gospel to the ends of the world. Fifth is the Acts 6:1-2 co-existence of Hellenistic and Hebraic Jews who ate freely from the same table in Jerusalem.

Sixth is Paul's conviction and call to see all humankind reconciled to God (2 Corinthians 5:19-20) and a vision of God's Kingdom without boundaries (Colossians 1:19-20). Notably, the Church growth recorded in the Acts of Apostles was inclusive across all social and cultural barriers, and the New Testament hardly recorded any homogenous Church system. At the Jerusalem Council in Acts 15, the Apostles laid to rest the agitation of the Jews to have the converted Hellenists observe Judaistic rites to be qualified for salvation. Apostle Paul argued that if the same Holy Spirit baptised the Gentiles as much as the Jews, then in Christ, there is no Jews or Greek, free or bound, male or female, but one Lord, one Spirit, and one body of Christ with diverse members of varying cultural orientation (Galatians 2:7-9; 3:26-29; Romans 1:16; 10:12; Colossians 3:10-11).

Multicultural Church Models of the Early Church

The two identified Churches in the Book of Acts are the Jerusalem and Antioch Churches. They present the first two models of the multicultural Church system in the early church. De Young et al. (2003) note, "On the day of Pentecost, the Jerusalem congregation grew from 120 Galilean Jews to over 3,000 multicultural, multilingual Jews. The church was multicultural and multilingual from the first moment of its existence." The Jerusalem Church was predominantly Jewish, with a strong Judaistic influence on their worship and administration (Acts 11:2-3). Although it comprises a significant Grecian population, two levels of leadership are easily noticeable.

Hebraic Jews led the higher hierarchy, while the lower was led by Hellenistic Jews (Acts 6:1-5). As a result, this administrative system identified above in such a multicultural system is bicultural. The lower leadership, comprising of the selected deacons, administered the practical side of the church ministry as it related to the welfare of the Grecian widows, among other things. In contrast, the upper leadership was concerned with the socio-religious burdens of the Hebraic Jews, which in no way meant a culturally biased prorated caste system.

In the same vein, the Antioch Church was planted as believers fled the persecution at Jerusalem. Jewish Christians who were scattered abroad went everywhere preaching; by this, Jews and Greeks were added to the Church (Acts 11:19-27). The pax-Romana doctrine of the Greco-Roman world enabled the multicultural representation of the church at Antioch.

Hence, the church at Antioch started as a multicultural Church. The presence of synagogues in most Roman cities enabled the curious pluralistic religious Greeks who sought every new form of knowledge to encounter the believing Jews who preached Christ. They dialogued with the Judaistic worshippers about whether Jesus was the Messiah. The Christians demonstrated the Holy Spirit's power through miracles, signs, and wonders, thus drawing the attention of other Hebraic Jews who sought after signs (1 Cor. 1:22).

Therefore, the missionary Churches planted by Paul were another multicultural church noticed in the Acts of the Apostle. They replicated the multicultural system at the church of Antioch in relation to Jerusalem but undoubtedly were administered autonomously. The churches were united by the Roman Empire's infrastructural network that connected the cities and towns through land and sea routes. The Roman Empire's globalisation effort also united the Greco-Roman world through language uniformity (Greek and Latin were the *lingua franca*). At the same time, the administrative structure divided the vast Empire into governing units of protectorates. These mentioned reasons, courtesy of the globalisation drive of the Roman Empire, ensured a multicultural urbanisation of such cities, hence, the churches too. Consequently, logistical and sociological barriers to the Gospel's spread and the inclusion of all *ethnos* were easily surmounted through the missionary efforts of Apostle Paul and the Churches he planted.

Distinctive of a Multicultural Church

- 1. Adaptability:** is the ability of the host culture to accommodate other cultures without the presupposition of dominance but rather of tolerance, and the minorities' survival instincts to accommodate culture shock, acculturate quickly and cope with discrimination. Adaptability is a hallmark of a witnessing and welcoming multicultural church. According to Fulkerson (2007), adaptability is "a situational competence which is an inherently flexible and habituated capacity to incorporate practices and manoeuvre knowledge and resources to survive in a racist society." Without this, the church becomes an accommodationist that only tolerates foreign cultures for as long as it permits dominance and subjugation.

- 2. Fair representation:** refers to how a multicultural church membership must be reflected in its multicultural leadership structure system. Such a system ensures that power is brokered and decisions are made across all cultural groups. Multicultural leadership abhors discrimination on no grounds, be it racial, social, economic, or sexual. Tahaafe-Williams K. (2012) comments that "as long as decision-making and power are in the hands of a particular racial, ethnic, or cultural group, then fundamentally it has failed to act justly and has not fulfilled the requirements of a multicultural church."
- 3. The Lingua Franca:** is a situation where a multicultural church adopts the language of trade used in daily public interactions within its situated society, especially a unifying one across the geographical polity of their existence. Such engendered the viral success of Paul's missionary efforts because the dominant Greco-Roman worldview shaped ethos, language, and socio-political outlook across the Empire. All the cultures were unified into a single governable entity, with the Romanicised Greek Language becoming the lingua franca across all Roman provinces. Therefore, Apostle Paul, being bicultural, a full-blooded Jew and Roman, employed his academic acumen to interpret and expound the Septuagint to the growing Greek converts while also speaking Aramaic among the Jewish communities in the Diaspora. However, where local traditions and cultural practices existed within the Empire, the Roman enculturation drives still overrode these for economic and socio-political advantages.
- 4. Heterogeneous Worship and Liturgy:** a multicultural Church avoids being mono-cultural in its order of programs, small group structure, and worship services. It was the first limitation of the Jerusalem Church in that they could not break free from Judaism's rituals, customary practices, and Mosaic order of worship (Acts 21:17-26). The Laws of Moses became the foundation of the earliest traditions of the early Jerusalem Church (Acts 15:1; 21:21). The Antioch church broke out of this Jerusalem Church narrative as they converted both Greeks and Jews. These conversions drew into the Church the Jews and Gentiles alike, Africans, Romans, Cretans and Cypriots, nobles or commoners; they worshipped in *koinonia* in one accord and became subsumed

into one identity, Christians. Apostle Paul vehemently opposed Peter when he seemed swayed by Jewish tendencies of a racial superiority complex at Antioch (Gal. 2:11-17).

5. **Intentionality:** the attitude that deliberately builds a multicultural system into the church rather than assuming it will develop over time. Intentionality involves a mutual communal lifestyle that promotes respect and understanding of individual cultural differences to foster bridge-building through beneficial relationships and shared access to leadership. Intentionality cuts across developing multicultural worship methodologies with inputs and participation from all cultural units. It strives to weave different experiences and rituals into its worship using inclusive images, symbols, and language that honour and respect different cultural traditions and spirituality (Tahaafe-Williams, 2011).
6. **Intercultural communication:** is the process of initiating, sending, transmitting, and receiving information within an intercultural context (Nema, 2020). Information is sent and received across a barrier of perception, which forms filters through which messages are encoded by the sender or decoded by the receiver. These cultural perspectives are major issues within the church's quest to attain a multicultural faith community. Intercultural communication accounts for the cultural peculiarity that forms the background through which a concept is interpreted and understood in a particular culture. Issues arise in a multicultural church when matters are subjectively engaged from the cultural viewpoints of the individual members.

Intercultural Communication Models and Paradigms

The first is Ralph Winter's Model, which categorises cross-cultural evangelism as E-1, E-2, and E-3 evangelism (Winter, 1975), with E-0 later added. These categories are communication barriers between a missionary and another culture. It is opined that communication issues within this context are directly proportional to the extent of cultural differences between the two cultures involved (Hesselgrave, 1991). Ralph Winter's E-1 communication communicates the Gospel within one's cultural group in one's language and shared cultural values. E-2 communication communicates the Gospel to people in another sub-culture familiar with one's language and culture without much effort. E-

3 communicates the Gospel to people with an entirely different language and culture than one's own culture. Thus, the farther the Gospel travels, the stronger the intercultural communication issues that arise.

Another is Nida's Paradigm. Nida (1960) identified three elements in the process of communication, namely, the source (S), the message (M), and the receptor (R). He posits that within the framework of communicating the Gospel, God is the Source (S) of the revelation of the scriptures through human channels, using their natural language, culture, and ability to understand so that the Message (M) that is, God's plan of redemption would be understood by the earliest Receptors (R), which was the nation of Israel. Therefore, he opines that, for example, when Western European missionaries preach the Gospel to the black people of Africa, the Gospel is presented in a European cultural form different from the cultural viewpoint of the first receptors. Even though the Gospel remains the same, the form is adaptive.

Nida concludes that the communication of the Gospel should ensure that the contemporary "R" can respond to the "M" within the context of his own culture in substantially the same manner as the first "R" responded to "M" within the setting of the biblical culture (Nida, 1960)." This model is exemplified by Paul, a bicultural missionary (1 Corinthians 9:20 and 10:33), a Jew and a Roman, who demonstrated a clear difference between how he communicated the Gospel to the Jews in Antioch (Acts 13:13-52) and to the learned heathens in Athens (Acts 17). This model prevents (mal/mis)communication of the Gospel. The Gospel message is better absorbed in a cross-cultural context when it appeals to the worldview of the intended people. This model delivers cultural understanding that facilitates the contextualisation of the Gospel message and engenders intercultural harmony in a multicultural Church context.

In addition is Hesselgrave's Dimensions. David J. Hesselgrvae discusses seven dimensions of cross-cultural communication in his book "Communicating Christ Cross-Culturally (Hesselgrave, 1991). First is worldviews – ways of perceiving the world through the tinted glasses of one's cultural bias. Second are the cognitive processes- ways of thinking formed through social and educational exposures. Third is the linguistic forms, that is, ways of expressing ideas through language that reveal the intrinsic values in their culture. Fourth are behavioural patterns, that is, ways of acting and conforming to mutually acceptable social norms. Fifth

are social structures- ways of interacting according to socially codified systems. Sixth is the media influence, that is, ways of channelling the message that suggests that transmission media are not neutral. Seventh is the motivational resources, that is, ways of decision-making that vary from one cultural context to the other.

These dimensions profile intercultural communication approaches within a multicultural church system. A multicultural church will need to reflect on the paradigms, dimensions, and models of gospel communication from various perspectives, as discussed in this section, to avoid the issues of (mal/mis)communication arising when each cultural unit is not treated as a distinct group. Identifying cultural differences among the represented cultures in a Church community minimises the friction and conflicts that miscommunication may impose on the church.

Communication Issues in Multicultural Churches: The Nigerian Context

Ositelu (2002) categorised the Nigerian Church into the Old Mission Churches (who may today recognise themselves as independent are the Anglican, the Methodist, the Baptist, the Roman Catholic, the Presbyterian, and the ECWA, with others) and the African Independent Churches (whom today form the Gospel/Pentecostal/Charismatic/Aladura/Evangelical churches in Nigeria like the RCCG, the Winners' Chapel, the MFM, the CAC, the C&S, the CCC, the BLW, the DLBC and others). Ositelu (2002) agrees with Oshun (1981) that the formation of African Churches was a response to the Westernised system of Protestant Christianity of the white missionary that voided everything African as fetish and barbaric was, at best, monotonous. Conversely, Ayegboyin and Ishola (1997) disagree with this view.

On the one hand, the agitation against discrimination of African values and cultural symbols in worship and outside the church on the geopolitical front is the rising call for self-determination and sovereignty of the blacks from the colonial masters from the late 1800s to early 1900s. Nevertheless, Ayegboyin and Ishola (1997) opine that the formation of these Churches was a reactive step towards how the church altered the indigenisation policy of Rev Henry Venn (the Anglican Church Secretary) carried out by his successor Rev J.S. Hill following the

death of Samuel Ajayi Crowther. Henry Venn documented the need for white missionaries to train indigenes who would coordinate church activities, which Hill failed to execute after the death of Samuel Ajayi Crowther. At the heart of this is the miscommunication of the main elements of the Gospel without the cultural biases of the Europeans and the subsequent failure to plant the Gospel on African soil with the African context. Ositelu (2002) asserts that the white missionaries emphasised European culture more than the biblical gospel truth. History is rife with problems arising in the Nigerian church concerning multiculturalism.

The Daily Independent newspaper, on September 13, 2005, reported that the Bishop of Calabar, Rt. Rev. Tunde Adeleye's admonition at the consecration of three Bishops that if care is not taken, some churches may close down, not because some members died, but because they have failed to agree on tribal lines (WWRN, 2005). The paper noted that the caution came "as tribalism had prevented some Anglican clergymen from assuming positions in areas outside their indigenous communities (WWRN, 2005)." Bunderson (2013) accounts that the Catholics of the diocese in Ahiara, who wanted one of their own appointed as bishop over them, rejected the appointment of Bishop Okpaleke, who hails from Awka in Anambra State because he is not an ethnic Mbaise in Imo State. Mbamalu (2016) ascribes one of the reasons for the protracted leadership tussle in the Assemblies of God Nigeria (AGN) to the failure of the church in transiting from a local indigenous ecclesiastical body known as the Church of Jesus Christ to a national and international Christian organisation following their affiliation to the Assemblies of God, America without losing the "bonds and boundaries of the locality." He posits that even though the minority ethnic groups ordained indigenes cannot break the hegemony of the Igbo-dominated leadership structure, the apex leadership tussles are tied to discrimination among Igbos of different ethnic extractions. Convincingly, it is obvious that the higher proportion of the non-Igbo population in the AGN was beginning to identify a lacuna of inequality, inequity, unfairness, injustice and unrighteousness (Aja, 2006).

Currently, the Nigerian church has a limited volume of literature that addresses issues of intercultural conflicts within her fold. Usually, it is not uncommon to find many indigenous Pentecostal and African Churches start as regional or local independent Churches. Notably, some

of the African Independent Churches which began in a particular tribe have extended beyond national boundaries and have achieved an international structure (Ositelu, 2002). With such increased spread across the country, intercultural issues that bother with communication and understanding arise. Among such are ethnic discrimination, claimed ownership of foremost leadership by an ethnic group, disproportionate leadership system that does not fairly represent the geographic spread of the church, intertwining of the founding ethnic group's cultural ideology with the religious ethos of the organisation and their political dominance over other groups.

Findings and Discussions of Contemporary Communication Issues in a Multicultural Church

Nema (2020) underscores that recent approaches in the study of intercultural communication emphasise the role of context in its interpretation of communication. He believes such context "is determined by the environment, shaped by the social, political and historical realities, that surrounds every person involved in the communication process." For this study, The Good Tidings Church, Ogbomoso, Nigeria, was chosen as a case study for the study of intercultural communication issues in a multicultural Church. This church was suitable because it is a missional Church that reaches out to disciple people from different cultures across various towns and villages through intercultural missions and Church planting endeavours.

The Missions Ministry arm of the church has implemented cross-cultural and multicultural church planting, reaching tribes across Sub-Saharan Africa for almost two decades. With a primary focus on immigrants in the northern senatorial district of Oyo State in southwestern Nigeria, bordering the Benin Republic, the ministry has encountered and laboured among fifteen distinct cultural people groups. As a missionary evangelist saddled with the pastoral responsibility of overseeing mission activities, one of these authors observed that communication issues between various ethnic groups in the mission fields limit the effectiveness of Church planting efforts among these people groups.

Since culture and communication are components of intercultural communication, and the two cannot be separated (Nema, 2020), this research is based on the analysis of data gathered from participant's

observations of the ethnic groups referred to above. Based on the investigation that lasted five years, the practical communication issues observed in these multicultural church planting tasks are:

- 1. Communicational friction due to Cultural Differences:** Each cultural group shares preset values formed over a long period and transferred from one generation to another regarding language, food, dress, attitudes, habits, and social behaviour or communications. This differentiates one group from another and leads to communicational friction along the lines of intercultural contact. Samovar & Porter (2004) observed that deep cultural structures often create the greatest problems for effective intercultural communication. These differences contribute to intercultural communication problems associated with Church planting and membership in a multicultural context.
- 2. Misinformed Perceptions due to Cultural Biases:** Cultural biases are the cultural lens that asserts correctness based on the observer's social and mind programming. As opined by Hofstede (1991), "culture is software and mental programming of the mind," these biases influence how a concept is processed and adapted in a given context. This determines how a practice is considered primitive and barbaric in one culture by the other. Such biases regulate cultural norms and affect the affection or acceptance of one culture to another in a multicultural communication context. Such biases further lead to stereotypes. Avruch (2004) described perpetual differences among ethnically different people groups within the same community, resulting in miscommunications, misunderstandings and internal intercultural conflicts.
- 3. Dominance Syndrome due to Cultural Hegemony:** Cultural hegemony is the superiority complex of the dominant culture over the other. As the Jews in Acts 15 required Gentile converts to become circumcised after the order of Mosaic Law and Paul's defence against such in Galatians 2, a cultural distrust happens between cultures when one claims ethnocentrism over others. In this case, one culture seeks to absorb the other into its mould of communication by adopting its signs, symbols and modes of communication as the acceptable form of communication in a multicultural context while dismissing the other(s) as impressionable or simplistic.

- 4. Uniformity issues versus Unity syndrome due to Cultural Segregation:** Cultural segregation is premised on division due to diversity. Cultural variations in demography present the problem of conflicting worldviews. Angela Nicholas (2019) notes that cultural heterogeneity negatively impacts the cohesiveness of groups due to its complexities. When not properly managed, diversity will contribute to disunity, acrimony, and segregation among groups within multicultural church communities. The problem arises because uniformity requires individual cultural units to give up their uniqueness and assimilate into a foreign culture considered superior. Cultures are distinctively unique and must, therefore, be treated as the unique identity of a people group.

Approaches to Communication in Multicultural Churches

This research identifies that intercultural communication problems in a multicultural church are better approached from multidimensional views, as highlighted below.

- 1. Intentional Approach:** Multicultural Churches emerge as intentional and collaborative efforts between visionary leadership and dynamic followership. A multicultural Church environment requires a deliberate strategic approach to create a warm climate that welcomes and celebrates cultural diversity. When a community of faith is transitioning from a mono-cultural to a multicultural Church system, it demands synergising the vision and mission of the local church with the *missio Dei*. Intentionality is driven by purposeful and visionary leadership that develops, empowers, and transfers the same to the people. The leadership creates the environment while the members witness the Gospel across all cultures represented in the larger society. Wright et al. (2015) observe that due to variations in preferred styles among diverse ethnic groups, an intentional system that caters for expressive styles that transcend racial barriers and welcomes all worshippers from different backgrounds ought to be the model for multicultural churches.
- 2. Sociological Approach:** Such involves implementing a multicultural system that accounts for the individual yearnings within the faith community. Dunlow (2017) ascribes importance to how church leadership culturally profiles and identifies the

- diversity of their congregation such that their teachings are adapted to reflect the sensitivity to such a diverse population. Dunlow's position is exemplified in Acts 6, where the Apostles heeded the Grecians' aspiration regarding daily food sharing. Sociological approaches concern equity, justice, fairness, activism, and social pressure that identify with the sociological needs of the cultural groups represented within the faith community and society. The multicultural church takes advantage of the fact that the Gospel is relevant to all sociological issues of humankind, from political oppression to economic exploitation, marginalisation, and injustice, to address problems peculiar to the people groups.
3. **Systematic Approach:** This involves a holistic approach to miscommunication issues in multicultural churches. The problems will be complex, and so will the approach too. The systematic approach analyses each issue as it arises within the community and seeks to identify solutions for each peculiar context. It attempts to avoid enforcing one streamlined solution that is expected to fit into all circumstances. From leadership to worship, programs, internal reconciliation, conflict resolution, and marriage, issues are addressed in ways that are peculiar to each given context.
 4. **Structural Approach:** These begin with the vision and mission statements as well as the administration of the church. Multicultural churches build their vision and mission statements on the biblical mandate of the church to bring all *ethnos* (people groups) into the *Ekklesia* (called-out people) of God. The structure of a Church administration must reflect a fair representation of the individual units forming its community. Zerai (2011), in her study where thirty per cent of a thousand church members are African-Americans, all the pastoral staff members were observed to be white. She thus asserts that multicultural church leadership should be a fair representation of the diversity in the congregation. Such diverse representation among the pastoral staff of multicultural churches will more likely encourage the growth of diverse populations.
 5. The structure must represent the demographics. The structure accounts for the cultural distance within the community, for example, between the rich and the poor, the educated and

unlettered, and the colour and the white races. The structure must be all-inclusive, from the leadership to language, forms, and imageries of worship and small cell units. Zerai (2011) posits that social cohesion in multicultural churches arises on the heels of societal racism. Thus, to achieve a cohesive congregation, the church leadership acknowledges and works with the congregants to build a God's kingdom on earth involving unified cultural diversity.

- 6. Theological Approach:** It involves *kenosis* and *catechism*. According to Phi 2:7, kenotic orthodoxy calls for emptying the self and all previously acquired traits, knowledge, and lifestyle to embrace the new (Gmainer-Pranzl, 2015). In a 2015 survey conducted via emails to 3,120 mainline Protestant churches using various names that connoted different racial backgrounds, Wright et al. (2015) found that more welcoming replies were sent to individuals with "white-sounding names" than others with ethnic names. This condition, termed "homophily", is the situation where churches are more open to worshippers from within their races and ethnic groups than others from outside of it is a prejudicial position inimical to the overall multicultural purpose of the church.

A multicultural system applies the kenotic orthodoxy principle through the immersion of members into new Christian cultures and worldviews that engender intercultural communication void of individual cultural biases. Kenotic orthodoxy is achieved through catechistic orthopraxy.

Catechistic orthopraxy is the indoctrination of new members of the faith community through discipleship-making processes into the practice of a lifestyle that extols the supremacy of the person and works of Jesus Christ anchored on the message of the Gospel as being above all human cultures (1 Cor. 3:3-9; Gal. 3:27-29). Catechism enables a multicultural church to build a Christ-centered-Gospel cultured Church insulated against the influences of any federating cultural units.

Marti (2009) describes this concept as an adoption of a new cultural identification termed "ethnic transcendence" in tandem with Paul's declaration in Gal. 3:28 that there is no longer Jew or Greek, slave or free, male and female; for you are all one in Christ Jesus. Marti asserts that the concept of "ethnic transcendence" reinforces members' worldview of a church connection based on a "shared religious identity"

without prejudice to the "value for their particular ethnicities." This is the most unifying communication approach that limits intercultural crises in the multicultural Church context.

Conclusion

This research has explored issues of intercultural in a multicultural church context. It identified communicational friction due to cultural differences, misinformed perceptions due to cultural biases, dominance syndrome due to cultural hegemony and uniformity issues versus unity syndrome due to cultural segregation as major intercultural problems complicating communication in the case study that was examined. The study suggested intentional, sociological, systematic, structural and theological approaches as the panacea to such intercultural communication problems in multicultural churches. Overall, the research concludes that these proffered solutions, when applied, consequently move congregants from fragile co-existence to a deep, long-lasting, committed relationship as a faith community bonded by a transcendent immaterial affinity.

Furthermore, in such Christian multicultural communities, this study opined that the congregants would be envisioned to view one another as family members and diverse parts of the same body, away from the "we versus them" ethnocentric worldview. This outcome would become evident with an image of a Christ-centered and gospel-cultured church environment where members live the gospel-transformed culture realities. Hence, intercultural communication becomes seamless because Christ and the Gospel are the language of communication.

Recommendations

Therefore, this paper recommends that:

1. The Church can be a model and agent for a fair, equitable, and just society if it begins with an internal revolutionising its cultural environment and practices to build an inclusive structure and worship systems that accommodate and tolerate varying cultural backgrounds.
2. The Church should embark on a transformational education of its members from cultural supremacists to compassionate believers who are as their Father wants all humankind to be saved and become members of His family on the earth and in heaven.

3. These issues are best resolved when transparent, unbiased and scripturally guided regular opportunities are provided for the congregation to openly discuss the vision, missions and practices of the church as they affect their general well-being as worshippers.
4. The Church in Nigeria is to inculcate intercultural studies as part of the training for Church workers, laity and clerical staff members. Theological educators can review their curriculum to include critical knowledge in multicultural ministry.
5. The Church leadership is to foster systematic Bible studies and preaching series that centre on the formation of a Christ-centred culture of one humanity-in-Christ to form a cohesive Christian community. Shared Christian experience as a community is achieved through programs that are inclusive and diverse in cultural orientations.
6. The Church is to encourage a strong discipleship process that leads to the emergence of strong leaders among cultural minorities within the organisation. These leaders are mentored to understand and imbibe the kingdom culture and historical development of the church to identify how the contributions of their cultural groups can be harnessed for the overall development of the church.
7. The Nigerian Church, across the divides of independent old mission churches and the independent indigenous denominations, should, as a matter of urgency, profile and process the yearnings of the individual group within its fold and respond with attitudes that promote togetherness and oneness. The church must promote Biblical values as a shared cultural identity within its body that forms the common foundation required for building a unified community despite the strain or burden of diversity.
8. Members need to communicate with one another within the purview of each other's cultural peculiarities. They can attempt to clarify from one another what a particular issue may mean from the speaker's perspective, thus avoiding a prejudicial interpretation of the receiver's worldview.
9. Christian worldviews that cut across all cultures through objective interpretation of biblical texts and their applications, void of cultural biases, are to be taught as a system of communication within the body of Christ.

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